

REINFORCING

Responsible tErritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open
Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance

D6.1 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

Grant Agreement Number: 101094435
Project Acronym: REINFORCING

Due date: 31/05/2023
Actual date: 31/05/2023
Document author/s: INMARK
Version: 1.0
Dissemination level: PU
Status: Final Version

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No.101094435.

Document History			
Version	Date	Comments	Author
0.1	19/05/2023	First Draft	Marina Tisner, INMARK
0.2	25/05/2023	Mapping projects for networking and joint activities	Luciana Ayciriex, INMARK
0.3	29/05/2023	Second Draft	Marina Tisner, Yolanda Ursa, INMARK
0.4	31/05/2023	Third and final draft	Angela Simone (coordinator), FGB

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

DEC: Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication

ERA: European Research Area

H2020: Horizon 2020

HEU: Horizon Europe

ORRI: Open and Responsible Research and Innovation

RRI: Responsible Research and Innovation

R&I: Research and Innovation

KPIs: Key Performance Indicators

WIDERA: Widening Participation and Strengthening the ERA Programme

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the REINFORCING Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (DEC), which is composed of the project's communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies and actions. This set of measures aims to increase the project's overall impact by introducing it to its key target audiences, create a deeper understanding of the project and its objectives, promote the project to raise awareness of ORRI benefits, and increasing visibility and participation in project services and grants; create synergies with ORRI related groups and other EU-funded projects and initiatives; and transfer knowledge generated by the project to stakeholder groups that can benefit from and exploit the project's results.

The DEC plan aims to achieve success by executing an integrated strategy for dissemination and exploitation alongside communication. Although the plan describes these elements separately, certain activities are closely linked.

The project's target audiences are a critical part of the REINFORCING DEC Plan, tailored to these specific audiences in mind. In addition, the plan will include an estimated execution timeline.

The REINFORCING DEC Plan is divided into six sections.

- **Chapter 1: DEC Objectives:** This chapter will describe the plan's communication, dissemination, and exploitation objectives.
- **Chapter 2: Target Audiences.** This chapter will describe the project's target audiences, which are critical to the plan and will be paramount to encourage the use of REINFORCING's One-Stop Source platform components, as well as raising the project's profile and establishing it as an exciting initiative toward ORRI that can intervene in different innovation ecosystems.
- **Chapter 3: Communication Strategy.** This chapter will describe the project's communication strategy, which is designed to promote the project and its results throughout its lifetime.
- **Chapter 4: Dissemination Strategy.** This chapter will describe the project's dissemination strategy, which is designed to transfer knowledge created by the project and disclose the project results to the people who can benefit from and best use them.
- **Chapter 5: Exploitation Strategy.** This chapter will describe the project's exploitation strategy, with focus on the actual use of key exploitable results (KER).
- **Chapter 6: Estimated Execution Timeline.** This chapter will provide estimated dates for planned project communication and dissemination and exploitation actions.
- **Chapter 7: Key Performance Indicators.** This chapter will describe the project's key performance indicators (KPIs), which will allow the consortium to measure the DEC plan's effectiveness in a quantitative and qualitative manner.

1. PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The REINFORCING project aims to become the ORRI central point of knowledge and expertise that supports territories and institutions in fostering Fair Transitions governance by aligning with societal values, needs, and expectations. REINFORCING will develop and deliver a One-Stop Source platform, which will serve as a hub, becoming the European entry-point to ORRI expertise, services, experiences, tools, resources, and practices for users from all types of institutions and quadruple helix sectors. The One-Stop Source will also be the central point of delivery of the ORRI support and financial activities, including cascading grants, support services (matchmaking services, mentoring, etc.), and ORRI training.

To maximize the impact of REINFORCING, the DEC plan aims to:

- Provide an integrated, solid, and common public image of the project, facilitating its recognition, raising awareness about it and attracting relevant target groups.
- Ensure the visibility of the project's actions, activities and events.
- Disseminate extensively the results of the project to the ORRI community, reaching out to newcomers in ORRI, such as policy makers, researchers, the general public, businesses, CSOs and NGOs, among others.
- Leverage on European and international partners networks and multipliers.
- Define a roadmap for the successful exploitation of all project outcomes.

The DEC plan is a strategic process to promote the project's actions and results throughout the project's lifetime. Although communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities sometimes overlap, they serve different purposes. As such, the objectives for each strategy vary, but they are meant to work in harmony. A strong communication strategy will help the project become known among REINFORCING's target audiences, thereby increasing its possibilities of disseminating generated knowledge and results in the future. On the other hand, a strong dissemination strategy will highlight the project's important work and demonstrate the enrichment created by EU-funded projects. Together, communication and dissemination create the groundwork for exploitation and sustainability. The exploitation strategy entails using the project results, i.e., the outputs generated by the project during its implementation.

DEC Integrated Approach

1.1 Communication Objectives

The project aims to use communication to inform its target groups about ORRI benefits and how REINFORCING supports institutional and territorial change in implementing ORRI. Thus, communication objectives focus on introducing the project, fomenting a more profound understanding, and consistently promoting it throughout its lifetime.

- **Introduce the project to REINFORCING's target audiences:** A successful introduction to the right groups is crucial to build momentum for the project. This will lay the groundwork for future communication about REINFORCING's progress and results.
- **Create a deeper understanding of the REINFORCING project objectives:** Communication measures and initiatives work to create a deeper understanding of the project. Developing this understanding will be beneficial when the project disseminates project results, as stakeholders will be able to identify why the project outcomes are relevant to them.
- **Promote REINFORCING and raise awareness about it:** It is crucial to promote REINFORCING and raise awareness about the importance of ORRI and REINFORCING support actions. This will help the project sustain momentum, ensuring that target groups are aware of the project throughout its lifetime and beyond.

1.2 Dissemination Objectives

By disseminating project results to specific target audiences, REINFORCING aims to create a cascade effect, triggering interest among relevant stakeholders and thereby maximizing the project's reach. The following are the project's dissemination objectives.

- **Transfer REINFORCING knowledge and outcomes to stakeholder groups that can use the information:** REINFORCING will disseminate project results to relevant stakeholder groups, including the scientific and research community, HEU-funded projects and actors, regions and territories, policy makers and citizens, to expand knowledge on ORRI benefits, increase the participation in cascade grants open calls and support the institutional change in implementing ORRI.
- **Create synergies with WIDERA grantees and further H2020 and HEU projects.** REINFORCING will disseminate project results to ORRI-related EU-funded projects, with a view to creating synergies and the early sharing of knowledge and evidence. REINFORCING will establish a dynamic two-way communication channel with relevant projects and initiatives to guide future joint actions.
- **Engage with key stakeholder groups to obtain feedback on project results:** The engagement aspect of the project, which is characterized by the creation of a two-way communication channel between REINFORCING and target stakeholder groups, is an important part of dissemination. It ensures that REINFORCING project results are discussed and considered for future initiatives and allows the consortium to consider comments and feedback from outside experts.

1.3 Exploitation Objectives

The REINFORCING consortium is committed to generate added value differentiated outputs and make the project unique and impactful. Thus, the exploitation objectives focus on ensuring the exploitation of the project results and making these results sustainable in the long term.

- **Increase the use of the project results by target groups.** Potential users of REINFORCING's outcomes, such as the One-Stop platform and support services, include R&I actors, territories, and policy makers across Europe, including Widening countries.

- **Identify pathways towards exploitation.** REINFORCING will pave the ground for a coherent exploitation and IP strategy. It will identify exploitation routes for relevant project results and ensure their future uptake by key players.
- **Demonstrate the generated impact of the project.** Built on the huge achievements in ORRI over the past decade and further strengthening the global ORRI community, REINFORCING will contribute to foster sustainable institutional and territorial changes towards ORRI and to reduce the existing disparities between institutions and territories in ORRI implementation.

2. TARGET GROUPS

Tailoring the project's communication and dissemination strategies to specific target audiences is important. This focused approach will ensure that information about REINFORCING gets to the right people: those who will be interested in the results and are open to possibly using them in the future.

REINFORCING's communication and dissemination efforts will focus on the following target groups. This targeting will define the tone, wording, and content produced by the project.

- **Scientific and Research community:** The Scientific and Research community involves higher education institutions and Research Performing Organizations (RPOs), among others. These groups can become ORRI knowledge generators and users of the One-Stop Source and will facilitate its uptake. They will contribute to increase awareness and implementation of ORRI and cascading grant calls. They are ORRI enablers and applicants to REINFORCING cascading grants open calls.
- **HEU Funded projects and actors:** These groups are an important target to enhance ORRI in their projects (e.g. projects dealing with AI-based systems that need to conduct sound due diligence for AI trustworthiness, covering societal robustness requirements. They include the EU Missions, Green Deal, EU Innovation Ecosystems and AI development. They can make use of the project results and facilitate its uptake and contribute to spread the benefits of ORRI implementation, build capacity in ORRI practices and respond to the cascading grant calls.
- **Innovation community:** The innovation community involves chambers of commerce, representatives of industry associations at regional, national and EU levels, social innovators and entrepreneurs. These groups can become ORRI knowledge generators and users of the project results, such as the One-Stop Source, and will facilitate its uptake. They will contribute to increase ORRI awareness and implementation, and the cascading grant calls, as well as to build capacity in ORRI practices. They are ORRI enablers and applicants to REINFORCING cascading grants open calls.
- **Regions and territories and all the relevant actors within it:** These regions include the widening regions and more those identified as lagging behind e.g., the Balkan region. They are the new ORRI knowledge generators and users of the project results. They will contribute to raise awareness of ORRI implementation and build capacity in ORRI practices. They are new ORRI enablers and applicants to REINFORCING cascading grants open calls.
- **Policy makers:** This group includes regional and national policy makers, foundations and funding agencies, EU institutions and units. Policy makers set the frameworks for R&I that look forward to support ORRI across Europe. REINFORCING will allow them to make informed policy decisions to promote the adoption of ORRI in different territories and institutions across Europe.
- **Citizens:** This group involves Civil Society organizations and European citizens, with focus on citizens from regions where the grantees are present. Citizens will be informed about the project to raise awareness about the importance of ORRI to align the R&I efforts to citizens expectations, needs and values.

3. COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

REINFORCING communication plan is built on three pillars: launch and connect, build momentum, and cascade to increase reach. Together, all three initiatives work in synergy to maximize project visibility and penetration. The communication plan also provides the necessary support for REINFORCING to execute its dissemination strategy and plan.

Launch and connect: The consortium will launch the project website and platform and create its social media channels. It then works to introduce REINFORCING and explain its objectives to target groups via the consortium’s sectorial and institutional networks.

Build momentum: After establishing the project, it is important to build momentum and maintain it by promoting REINFORCING’s first activities and cascading grant calls. This will ensure that the project is seen as active and innovative and will encourage target groups to follow it closely.

Cascade to increase reach: The project will create a communication cascade through which key actors pass along REINFORCING content and results to other key actors, ensuring maximum reach and impact. This will include launching email, social media and web campaigns so that REINFORCING followers can share project actions and progress.

3.1 *Communication Channels*

REINFORCING’s communication channels will help promote the project and create an understanding of its work. The following channels will position REINFORCING as the ORRI central point of knowledge and expertise, ensuring that target groups perceive REINFORCING as an exciting top-of-mind project. These channels will be used to promote the project upon launch and will remain active during and after REINFORCING’s conclusion.

3.1.1 *Project Platform and Website*

REINFORCING’s central communication channel is the project web platform (www.reinforcing.eu), which is the entry point to the project’s One-stop Source, RRI tools and resources and will be launched in M9. The platform will be regularly updated and structured around a new ORRI taxonomy, establishing the project’s online presence. Allocated on a website, it will inform key stakeholders about the project’s scope and keep target groups up to date on the progress of the REINFORCING project.

The tentative website structure will have the following sections:

- About: What’s the project about? What are its objectives & partners
- Reinforcing One-Stop Source Platform: How does it work, insights & guide
- News and events: Releases and updates about the project and important events
- Publications
- Newsletter Registration

3.1.2 Social Networks

Twitter and LinkedIn serve as the project's official social media channels because of their high levels of engagement and professional nature. These channels are used to advertise project events and open cascading calls, keeping stakeholders engaged with the community actions.

According to what was proposed in the DoA, social media profiles could be inherited from the previous EU Project RRI Tools, since so far they were a key point of reference for the RRI community. Negotiations are already ongoing for the institution in charge of the profiles, which hopefully will be activated as REINFORCING channels by the first six months of the project.

3.1.3 Partner networks and multipliers

REINFORCING partners have a far-reaching network of actors that enhance capacities to further develop RRI approach in different regional innovation ecosystems in Europe and worldwide. These networks will act as a unique multiplier to cascade REINFORCING objectives and results across relevant stakeholder communities. These networks include, but are not limited to, the European Business and Innovation Centre Network (EBN), the European Forum for Studies of Policies for Research and Innovation (EU-SPRI), ENRICH Global, the European Association of Research and Technology Organizations (EARTO), the Virtual Institute of Responsible Innovation (VIRI), the European Regions Research and Innovation Network (ERRIN), and the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA).

3.1.4 Events

Project events

The project will organize workshops, capacity-building training, online webinars, and networking events to expand ORRI knowledge. Examples of these activities include webinars with the grantees, which are focused on promoting grantees' activities after each round of grants to showcase outcomes and increase REINFORCING visibility among stakeholders. Furthermore, the project will organize side events at significant international and EU events, such as EU R&I days, the Euro Science Open Forum (ESOF), etc.

The project will also host an impact prize event in month 35 and a final project event in month 48, promoting its overall efforts and achievements and disseminating its results.

Tentative schedule of significant projects events:

Event	Tentative Date
Workshop involving key territorial and ORRI actors	June 2023
First workshop (online) with EU sister projects	September 2023
1st workshop (in Milan) to gather crowdsourced insights on ORRI Taxonomy	December 2023
2nd workshop on targeted community engagement (Balkans)	December 2023
International conference/Global Network	October 2024
Impact Prize events	November 2025
Policy Forum/ Final Event	December 2026

Third-party events

The consortium will explore if participating in relevant conferences and events related to ORRI and other topics for deepening the ERA. These events will allow the consortium to promote the project to target audiences, ensuring networking and engagement of stakeholders, sharing main findings and results with a broader community, and reach participants for the open calls. The tentative list of events that REINFORCING partners will attend during the project's first year is included below.

Event	Description	Date
European Week of the Regions and Cities	Dedicated to regional policy where regions and cities showcase their capacity to create growth and jobs, implement EU cohesion policy, and prove the importance of the local and regional level for good European governance.	9-12 October 2023
Open Science Conference	Forum for researchers, librarians, practitioners, infrastructure providers, policy makers, and other stakeholders to discuss the developments in Open Science.	27-29 June 2023
EuroScience Open Forum	The largest interdisciplinary meeting on science and innovation in Europe, for and with society.	13-16 July 2023
EBN Annual Congress	Gathers business incubation executives, corporate leaders, senior-level government officials, and innovation experts.	Open Innovation Workshop: 13-15 June 2023
Society for Social Studies of Science	Fosters interdisciplinary and engaged scholarship in science, technology, and society.	8-11 November 2023

3.2 Content Production for Communication Purposes

The project's content to be produced for communication purposes will focus on the project overview and its planned coordination and support activities. It is worth to highlight that the content for communication will be different from the content for dissemination, as described below in 4.2. The communication content will be customized according to the target group, purpose, communication channel and specific moment in time. Content will include, but is not limited to, the following topics:

- **REINFORCING project overview:** Content produced along this editorial line will include project objectives, scope, project services, planned activities and cascading open calls. and grants. The goal is to create an integrated, solid, and standard public image of the project, facilitating its recognition.
- **Promotion of REINFORCING One-Stop Source.** Content focused on the promotion of the platform will also be used to build momentum, gather possible participants to cascading grants open calls, and form relevant connections with key stakeholders to support institutional and territorial changes efficiently.
- **Promotion of REINFORCING project events and joint actions with relevant projects and initiatives:** Content will be devoted to communicating networking and joint activities and sharing results with other WIDERA grantees, further H2020 and HEU projects.

3.3 Communication materials

Communication materials are an important part of the project's strategy. These materials will support the project's promotional and multiplier activities and inform stakeholders on important project updates. The following are the communication materials

that have been created thus far. Nonetheless, more materials like videos, infographics, press releases, articles, or publications will be created throughout the project's lifetime.

Logo

The REINFORCING logo represents unity, connection, and progress.

The colour palette used in the logo with different types of blue represents strength, trust, and stability, like the European Union's flag. As regards the typography, it is intended to be clean, modern, and easily readable. Likewise, the tagline in the logo aims to make the project recognizable, bringing the target audience awareness and top of mind for materials such as deliverables, articles, or presentations.

The REINFORCING logo considers two different versions; the first includes a tagline that will be used for deliverables and templates. The second version will appear on the website and other digital channels like social media.

V.1. Logo with tagline

V.2 Logo for digital communications

In this second version, the logo will be reduced to the graphic design being easier to adapt and include in digital channels like websites and social media.

The logo typography and colour palette as well as other examples of application can be seen in Annex 1.

Press Release

Press releases on project objectives and activities will be issued for major milestones. They will be translated into partners' languages for local distribution if needed.

Project Presentation

The consortium will prepare a visually impactful presentation to provide a breakdown of the REINFORCING project, goals and activities. Partners will be able to use the presentation to introduce the project at third-party events and networking activities, among others.

4. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

Similar to the communication plan, REINFORCING dissemination plan is based on three pillars: communication as groundwork for dissemination, dissemination to target audiences, and dissemination campaigns for high-impact channels. It is designed to work in perfect synergy with the project's communication plan.

Communication as groundwork for dissemination: REINFORCING will focus on communication activities during the first year of the project in order to lay the groundwork for the successful dissemination of project results in year two. Dissemination activities in year two ensure that target groups are familiar with REINFORCING services, thereby increasing their receptiveness to using project results.

Disseminate to key target audiences: The second phase of REINFORCING's dissemination plan begins in year two at the moment when the One-Stop Source platform is operational and accessible. REINFORCING will begin to launch dissemination campaigns of project results through online and offline channels and will also work to generate engagement with key target groups.

Launch dissemination campaign in high-impact channels: The final dissemination phase will leverage the foundation and momentum developed during the first and second year of the project to increase the reach of project results. As the project progresses, the consortium will focus on dissemination in high-impact channels, such as the One-Stop Source platform, email marketing campaigns, project events, scientific publications, and institutional websites.

4.1 Dissemination Channels

The following are the main dissemination channels that will be used to transfer knowledge, tools, services, and results to key stakeholder groups. Some of these channels are also used in communication, which is natural in our online world. However, channels used for dissemination purposes will focus on transferring project generated knowledge and results.

4.1.1 Email marketing platform

REINFORCING will leverage MailChimp, an email marketing platform, to create targeted dissemination campaigns, e.g., newsletters, for each of REINFORCING target groups.

4.1.2 Social media, website, and One-Stop Source platform

The REINFORCING social media channels, website and One-Stop Source platform will also be used for dissemination purposes. These media will be used to disseminate curated content and research results to key stakeholders that support ORRI.

4.1.3 Scientific publications

Scientific publications will serve as channels that will deliver project results to the professional, scientific community. Examples of such research publications include [Open Research Europe](#), the *Journal of Responsible Innovation, Science and Public Policy*, *European Planning Studies*, *Journal of Responsible Technology*, *Regional Studies*, *Science and Engineering Ethics*,

and the *International Journal of Innovation Studies*, among others, will serve as channels that will deliver project results to the professional, scientific community.

4.1.4 Project events

REINFORCING workshops, webinars, the impact prize event and final conference will be used to directly disseminate project results to a carefully curated list of guests that are most likely to be interested in the project's results. These events will also be used to gather feedback that will contribute to and shape future project actions.

4.1.5 Networking and joint activities

The REINFORCING project is also working to develop close cooperation with other relevant projects to deepen the ERA, with a view to fostering collaboration and the early sharing of knowledge and results. Networking and joint activities are foreseen with projects funded under WIDERA to reform and enhance the EU research and innovation system. Close cooperation will be developed with ORRI-related projects and other relevant projects and initiatives dealing with open science, science education and communication, gender equality, ethics ORRI-related, and integrity.

The following projects and initiatives have been selected to explore networking and joint activities:

- [PATTERN](#) - Empowering ORRI by developing and piloting training activities for researchers at all stages of their careers.
- [COARA](#) - Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment: It sets a shared direction for changes in assessment practices for researchers and RPOs.
- [ECS](#) - European Citizen Science: This project aims to widen and strengthen the citizen science community in Europe through capacity-building and awareness-raising activities.
- [ROSiE](#) - Responsible Open Science in Europe: The project develops tools to ensure ethics and research integrity in open science and citizen science.
- [OPUS](#) - Open Universal Science: This project will develop coordination and support measures to reform the assessment of researchers.
- [PathOS](#) - Open Science Impact Pathways: This project aims to identify and quantify the Key Impact Pathways of Open Science relating to the research system and its interrelations with economic and societal actors.
- [GILL](#) - Gendered Innovation Living Labs: The project will develop a pan-European collaboration and learning hub for open-gendered innovation.
- [BEYOND](#) - Beyond Bad Apples: Towards a Behavioural and Evidence-Based Approach to Promote Research Ethics and Research Integrity in Europe: The project promotes adherence to the highest standards of research ethics and integrity and prevent research misconduct.
- [GENDER STI](#) - Gender Equality in Science, Technology, and Innovation in Bilateral and Multilateral Dialogues: The project investigates how gender equality is taken into consideration at different levels of international cooperation dialogues in STI.
- [ETHNA System](#) - Ethics Governance System for RRI in Higher Education, Funding, and Research Centres: The project will develop and implement an ethics governance system for grounding good practices in RRI in higher education. It will produce a code of ethics and good practices in R&I for use by RPOs and RFOs.
- [Co-Change](#) - Co-Create Change in Research Funding and Performing: The project entails centres on the concept of change labs to generate transformative capacity for institutional change. It provides RRI self-evaluation, impact assessment, and a toolbox.
- [INCENTIVE](#) - Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society.
- [TIME4CS](#) - Supporting sustainable Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science in Science and Technology.

4.2 *Content Production for Dissemination Purposes*

The content for dissemination will focus on project results to produce engaging material to transfer knowledge that relevant stakeholders, such as the One-Stop Source platform and ORRI Guidelines, can use. In addition, content for dissemination will also focus on and ORRI resources and tools created by REINFORCING, such as cascading grants supporting documents, lessons learned on ORRI training, or final policy recommendations. The content and tools will be customized according to the target group, purpose, dissemination channels, and the specific moment in time, among others. Promoting project results extensively to the existing ORRI community and reaching out to newcomers in ORRI, such as policymakers, the research community, the general public, businesses, GSOs and NGOs, will create pathways to exploitation.

Content and tools will include, but are not limited to, the following:

- **ORRI Guidelines:** This report will include comprehensive and up-to-date guidelines for the achievement of meaningful and sustainable institutional changes within all areas of ORRI. The guidelines will provide support to selected grantees as well as the community at large in the implementation of their ORRI initiatives.
- **Cascading grants supporting documents:** The content produced and released on the project website and platform contains support documents for REINFORCING cascading grants applicants, such as guidelines for applicants, FAQ, Application Form templates, and progress reporting templates.
- **Lessons learned on ORRI training:** A brief report on lessons learned about ORRI training modules will be produced, including training of grantees about ORRI principles; crash courses to level up specific ORRI needs that emerged from interaction with the community, and ORRI clinics to collaboratively address specific challenges faced by the community.
- **Policy Briefs:** A policy brief will be produced at the end of each reporting period. Content will be concise, readable, and focus on REINFORCING results and knowledge to support policy recommendations.
- **Policy Recommendations:** Content will consider a suite of Policy Briefs targeted at key user groups, such as decision-makers in institutions and territories aiming to reach higher levels of ORRI.

5. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

The REINFORCING exploitation strategy is envisioned to work harmoniously with the implementation of dissemination actions and measures. Whilst disseminating the knowledge and results of REINFORCING will be essential for triggering impact and interest among relevant stakeholders, exploitation will focus on the actual use of the project results, both by the consortium partners and by target users outside the consortium, in view to make the results long-lasting.

The exploitation plan will be developed in three steps throughout the project:

- Identify key exploitable results.
- Explore pathways to exploitation.
- Create an action plan for sustainability.

All partners will discuss exploitation issues based on a consensus-made decision process. Three internal exploitation meetings be held during project meetings (M15, M21, and M33).

5.1 Key Exploitable Results (KER)

The Consortium has elaborated a preliminary list of Key Exploitable Results (KER) that will be refined as the project evolves, exploring possible exploitation routes and potential users for each.

Key Exploitable Results	Exploitable route	Potential users
One-Stop Source platform	Open Dissemination	R&I actors, territories, policy makers
Trainings, mentoring services and pathways	Open Dissemination	R&I actors, territories, policy makers
ORRI tools	Open Dissemination	R&I actors, territories, policy makers

For each exploitable result, the following features will be identified: clarification of the nature of the result, form(s) of exploitation of these results and identification of risks and actions to mitigate them, as well as existing or emerging alternative solutions.

Taken together, these project outcomes provide a unique toolkit to support territories and institutions in the implementation of ORRI across Europe.

5.2 Pathways to Exploitation

The consortium will work to ensure a successful knowledge transfer and a coherent exploitation and IP strategy. It will identify relevant exploitation routes for REINFORCING results in order to guarantee their future uptake by relevant players.

In addition, the exploitation plan will outline the individual partners' vision and plan to use the project outcomes within their strategies to transfer knowledge and use the platform and services in their business and further research activities.

5.3 Action Plan for Sustainability

The action plan for sustainability will be delivered towards the end of the project (D6.3) to ensure the impact and sustainability of the project results beyond its lifetime. The action plan will work in harmony with the project's exploitation plan. It will define specific actions that will be undertaken after the project phase, including responsibilities, the expected impact of implementation, metrics, and third parties involved.

6. ESTIMATED EXECUTION TIMELINE

The following is an estimated execution timeline of REINFORCING communication and dissemination activities. Like the Communication and Dissemination Plan itself, the timeline is fluid and can be modified as required by the project.

6.1 Communication Estimated Timeline

Year 1: Reinforcing launch, communication channels and identify target audiences													
M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12		
REINFORCING project launch. Creation of website, One-Stop Source platform and custom social media channels						Present REINFORCING to target groups. Communication package release introducing project objectives.							
Year 2: End consolidating evidence based and start gathering project results													
M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24		
Promote trainings, webinars and workshops to ORRI Enablers and HEU Funded projects and actors						Launch email social media and web campaign promoting International Conference to ORRI enablers & HEU funded projects and actors							
Year 3: Build momentum with project results													
M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36		
Promote mid-project results to applicants to REINFORCING cascading grants and open calls						Promote dissemination of results at third-party events. Launch email social media and web campaign promoting impact prize event							
Year 4: Cascade results to ensure maximum reach													
M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48	M49	M50
Promote training activities and new resources to each target group						Launch email, social media and web campaign promoting the publication of results and final conference						Promote recommendations	

6.2 Dissemination Estimated Timeline

Year 1: Use communication to lay groundwork for dissemination													
M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12		
Communication activities													
Year 2: End consolidating evidence based and start targeting key stakeholders													
M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24		
Launch targeted email campaigns to REINFORCING list of key stakeholders with first project evidences and available resources						Present first results at project events, trainings and workshops as well as at third party events							
Year 3: Begin dissemination to key target audiences													
M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36		
Launch targeted email campaigns to ORRI enablers & HEU funded projects and actors with mid-project results and upcoming events						Launch targeted email campaigns to REINFORCING cascading grants applicants with mid-project results and resources							
Year 4: Launch targeted dissemination campaign in high-impact channels													
M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48	M49	M50
Publish results in a targeted ORRI industry publications likely to be read by key stakeholders. Send results to REINFORCING identified target audiences using established channels						Host final project event and present results and publications to a curated list of the projects target audiences						Promote recommendations	

7. KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

In order to ensure that the REINFORCING Communication and Dissemination Plan is maximizing the project's impact and increasing its reach, we will measure the plan's efficiency with quantitative and qualitative indicators. Should significant deviation occur, e.g., a failure to achieve objectives set in three or more indicators, the consortium will adapt the plan and adopt the necessary measures to get the project back on track.

Nonetheless, the plan is a living document and will be continuously adapted and optimized to meet the project's needs.

Quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) refer to those that can be measured with analytics tools, e.g., website visits and other means of numerical measurement. Meanwhile, qualitative KPIs are those that cannot be easily measured through numerical means. An example of this includes community engagement and responses to content.

Given that some channels are used in both communication and dissemination strategies and some indicators will be included in both communication and dissemination.

7.1 *Communication KPIs*

KPIs for the project's communication aim to ensure the project and the reach of European R&I in general are promoted to the project's key stakeholders. The communication actions will lay the groundwork for the project's dissemination actions by informing stakeholders of its goals and research questions.

7.1.1 *Quantitative Indicators*

Indicator Description	Means of verification
Availability of REINFORCING Platform	Platform online 24/7
Website visits	12.000 visits (at least 3.000/year)
Third-Party events attended by project partners	25-30 events (at least 5/year)
Number of presentations about the project at third party events	At least 15 presentations
Social media followers (Twitter)	At least 6.500 followers (from RRI Tools profile)
Newsletters	At least 4 (one per year)
Project news articles on website	At least 10 articles

7.1.2 *Qualitative Indicators*

Indicator Description
Mentions by other project initiatives or agencies
Contributions to other actions
Proactive online community in project webinars

7.2 *Dissemination KPIs*

The aim of dissemination is to transfer project generated to knowledge to stakeholders that can benefit from it. Therefore, dissemination KPIs will focus on the transfer and engagement with project results.

7.2.1 Quantitative Indicators

Indicator Description	Means of verification
Number of social media campaigns with project results	At least 4
Participation in ORRI related conferences and events	At least 25 events during the project
Publish REINFORCING results in scientific journals	At least 5 abstracts and papers in different journals
Number of capacity building and training activities	At least 10
Number of workshops and online webinars	At least 50
Number of attendees to mid-term international conference	80-100 key ORRI audience members
Number of attendees to project final event	At least 20 key policy makers

7.2.2 Qualitative Indicators

Indicator Description
Mentions by other project initiatives or agencies
Contributions to other actions
Proactive online community in project webinars

ANNEX 1: REINFORCING LOGO

	C 94 M 54 Y 53 K 56	R 1 G 58 B 65	# 013a41
	C 85 M 32 Y 41 K 18	R 0 G 117 B 128	# 007580
	C 74 M 4 Y 26 K 0	R 3 G 175 B 192	# 03afc0
	C 59 M 0 Y 11 K 0	R 100 G 197 B 224	# 64c5e0

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